

Insect resistance

Varietal reaction to rice panicle bug

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In 1982-83 kharif, we screened 37 entries from the Rice Coordinated Yield Trials for field reaction to rice bug *Leptocorisa acuta*. The trial was in a randomized block design with three replications. Twenty-five-d-old seedlings were planted in 20-m² plots at 20- × 10-cm spacing. Recommended agronomic practices were followed, but no insecticide was applied. Insect population was recorded in a 1-m² area at 4 sites in each plot early in the morning 70 d after planting. Resistance was scored using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES).

IET5860, IRTP08506, IET5878, Pusa 312, TKM9 (popular variety of Chingleput District), and TNAU18580 were moderately resistant to the bug. The remaining 31 entries were either susceptible or highly susceptible (see table). □

Genetics of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) resistance in IET5741

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IET5741 was identified as resistant to WBPH during screening of various rice accessions and varieties at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore. We studied the genetics of resistance of ET5741 by crossing it with IR36, a WBPH-susceptible variety. The F₁ seedlings were resistant to WBPH, indicating the dominant nature of IET5741 resistance (see table). The F₂ population segregated in a 3:1, resistant: susceptible ratio, indicating that the resistance is conditioned by a single

Varietal reaction to rice panicle bug at Tirur, Tamil Nadu, India, 1982.

Variety	Parentage	Duration (d)	Mean no. of bugs/m ²	Resistance score ^a
IET5860	RPA 5824/RPA 79-9	97	2	3
IRTP08506	- B	113	2	3
IET5878	ala late mutant	105	3	3
Pusa 312	Karjat 35/N22	108	3	3
TKM9	TKM7/IR8	108	3	3
TNAU18580	IR20/Vani	107	4	3
TNAU18328/1	Kannagi/Cul2032	110	7	7
ACM3	Bhavani/CO36	107	9	7
TNAU80029	IR20/Balawi/IR2071-625-1-252	110	9	7
ADT36	Triveni/IR20	107	10	9
BPHR3	PTB33/IR3403-267-1-4	107	11	9
ACM2	Kannagi/IR28	110	11	9
IR50	IR2153-14-1-6-2/IR28/IR36	110	11	9
BS26	CO13/IR26	109	12	9
IET5253	Cauvery/W12787	109	12	9
AD18485	Triveni/Annapooma	107	12	9
AS688	ADT31/Ratna//ASD8/IR8	97	13	9
AD24417	Kannagi/CH41	109	14	9
AS19703	ADT30/ADT16	110	15	9
ACM1	CO 13/IR26	107	15	9
TNAU2099	GEB24/IR30	110	16	9
BPHR10	Ratuhinati/IR3408-267-1-3	109	16	9
DPI962	IR26/TKM6	109	17	9
AD25723	CO 33/IR266/CO33//IET2222	109	18	9
DPI1091/1	IR20/Kannagi	110	19	9
CO 34	TN1/CO 29	109	19	9
IET4786	CR10-114/CR115	100	20	9
BPHR5	IR3403-267/PTB33/IR36	110	21	9
TNAU9426/6	Kannagi/Cul2032	98	23	9
TM8089	TKM9/selection	107	24	9
BS27	CO 13/IR26	107	24	9
AD24155	ADT31/CO40	109	24	9
BS36	CO 13/IR26	109	24	9
CO37	TN1/CO 29	110	27	9
TM8090	TKM9 selection	109	28	9
BS37	IR26/CO 13	109	36	9
DPI1091-5	IR20/Kannagi	110	47	9

^a By 1980 SES.

Reaction to WBPH in F₁, F₂, and F₃ progenies of the cross between IET5741 and IR36, Coimbatore, India.

Cross	Reaction ^a to WBPH						
	F ₂ seedlings			F ₃ families			
	R (no.)	S (no.)	X ² 3:1	R (no.)	Seg (no.)	S (no.)	X ² 1:2:1
IET5741/IR36	171	63	0.4616	44	105	51	0.99

^a R = resistant, S = susceptible, Seg = segregating.

dominant gene. The F₃ segregated to 1 resistant: 2 segregating: 1 susceptible,

which further confirmed the monogenic nature of IET5741 resistance to WBPH. □